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New species and new records of leaf beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) from Thailand and Vietnam

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Abstract. Eight new species of leaf beetles are described from Thailand and Vietnam: *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n., *Japonitata insolita* sp. n., *Monolepta quadrifoveolata* sp. n., *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n., *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n., *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., and *Phygasia oblongomaculata* sp. n. The following 13 species are recorded from Thailand for the first time: *Lema impressipennis* Pic, 1944, *Cryptocephalus flavicinctus* Jacoby, 1892, *Trichochrysea cephalotes* (Lefèvre, 1893), *Apophyllia borowieci* Bezděk, 2004, *Apophyllia clypeata* Samoderzhenkov, 1988, *Atysa brevicornis* (Samoderzhenkov, 1988), *A. gressitti* (L. Medvedev, 2005), *Paridea glyphea* Yang, 1993, *Chaetocnema yunnanica* Heikertinger, 1951, *Hyphasis trilineata* L. Medvedev, 2008, *Philopona shima* Maulik, 1928, *Yunotrichia mediovittata* Chen et Wang, 1980, and *Cassida rati* Maulik, 1923. Figures of habitus and genitalia are given for all new for science and some related species, as well as for some of newly recorded species. The male habitus and the aedeagus of *Atysa brevicornis* previously known only from females are imaged for the first time. New morphological data on the rare species *Sinoluperoides chenchirae* Romantsov, 2025 and *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* Romantsov, 2025 are presented. An auxiliary identification key to the *Phygasia* Chevrolat, 1836 species with black body and a pale spot on each elytron is compiled.

Key words: Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Thailand, Vietnam, new species, new records.

Новые виды и новые указания жуков-листоедов (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) из Таиланда и Вьетнама

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Резюме. Описано восемь новых видов листоедов из Таиланда и Вьетнама: *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n., *Japonitata insolita* sp. n., *Monolepta quadrifoveolata* sp. n., *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n., *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n., *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., *Phygasia oblongomaculata* sp. n. Следующие 13 видов впервые зарегистрированы в Таиланде: *Lema impressipennis* Pic, 1944, *Cryptocephalus flavicinctus* Jacoby, 1892, *Trichochrysea cephalotes* (Lefèvre, 1893), *Apophyllia borowieci* Bezděk, 2004, *Apophyllia clypeata* Samoderzhenkov, 1988, *Atysa brevicornis* (Samoderzhenkov, 1988), *A. gressitti* (L. Medvedev, 2005), *Paridea glyphea* Yang, 1993, *Chaetocnema yunnanica* Heikertinger, 1951, *Hyphasis trilineata* L. Medvedev, 2008, *Philopona shima* Maulik, 1928, *Yunotrichia mediovittata* Chen, Wang, 1980 и *Cassida rati* Maulik, 1923. Даны изображения габитуса и гениталий всех новых для науки и некоторых родственных видов, а также некоторых видов, впервые зарегистрированных в Таиланде. Впервые даны изображения габитуса самца и эдеагуса *Atysa brevicornis*, ранее известного только по самкам. Представлены новые морфологические данные о редких видах *Sinoluperoides chenchirae* Romantsov, 2025 и *Paleosepharia magnitarsis* Romantsov, 2025. Для видов рода *Phygasia* Chevrolat, 1836 с черным телом и светлым пятном на каждом надкрылье предложена вспомогательная определительная таблица.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae, Thailand, Vietnam, новые виды, новые указания.

The present study has resulted in description of eight leaf beetle species new for science, and 13 leaf beetle species are recorded for Thailand for the first time. Morphological characters and geographical distribution of some species are clarified, as well as an identification key for representatives of the genus *Phygasia* Chevrolat, 1836 with body black and a pale spot on each elytron is given.

The paper is based on the examination of the material collected by the author in Northern Vietnam in 2018–2019 and in the mountains of Northern Thailand (near Thep Sadet village located on the Khun Tan Range) in 2024–2025. In addition, material from Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (ZIN, St Petersburg, Russia), as well as from the author's collection (PR, St Petersburg, Russia) were studied.

All measurements were made using an ocular grid mounted on MBS-20 stereomicroscope. Measurements of

all segments were taken at their widest part, unless otherwise specifically stated. All the proportions of antennomeres and tarsomeres are given in standard units (1 conventional unit = 0.025 mm). Measurements are given only for visible tarsomeres, that is, for ones I–III and V. All photos were taken by the author. Photographs of habitus were taken using a Canon EOS 80D digital camera with a combined Canon EF 70–200 mm f/4.0L IS USM and inverted following lenses: Olympus OM-System Zuiko Auto-T 100 mm f/2.8 for large species, Minolta MC Rokkor-PF 50 mm f/1.7 or Canon EF-S 60 mm f/2.8 Macro USM for medium size species and Olympus Zuiko Digital 35 mm f/3.5 Macro for small size species. Photographs of aedeagi and spermathecae were taken using a Canon EOS 80D digital camera and a combined Canon EF 70–20 mm f/4.0L IS USM and inverted Canon EF-S 24 mm F2.8 STM lenses (to photograph spermathecae Canon Extender EF 1.4 X II

was additionally used). Images at different focal planes were combined using Zerene Stacker Professional 1.04 software.

Subfamily Criocerinae Latreille, 1804
Genus *Lema* Fabricius, 1798

Oriental species of *Lema* were reviewed and keyed by Warchałowski [2011].

Lema impressipennis Pic, 1944

Material. 1♂, 1♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1285-1458 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'10", E 99°22'47" 20.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."; 1♂ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1125-1310 m, N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 28.V.2025".

Distribution. Laos and Vietnam [Warchałowski, 2011], Northern Thailand (first record).

Subfamily Cryptocephalinae Gyllenhal, 1813
Genus *Cryptocephalus* Müller, 1764

Cryptocephalus (s. str.) *flavicinctus* Jacoby, 1892

Material. 1♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 15.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."; 1♂ (PR), the same data, but "20.V.2025"; 1♂ (PR), the same data, but "22.V.2025"; 1♂ (PR), the same data, but "25.V.2025"; 2♂, 1♀ (PR), the same data, but "26.V.2025".

Distribution. China, Myanmar [Duan et al., 2025], Vietnam (as *C. pallidilabris* Pic, 1930) [Kimoto, Gressitt, 1981], Thailand (first record).

Subfamily Eumolpinae Hope, 1841
Genus *Trichochrysea* Baly, 1861

The genus *Trichochrysea* was reviewed and keyed by Medvedev and Eroshkina [1987]. Their later work [Medvedev, Eroshkina, 1999] was devoted to the *Trichochrysea* species from Thailand. In addition, an identification key to the oriental *Trichochrysea* species by Kimoto and Gressitt [1982] was compiled.

Trichochrysea cephalotes (Lefèvre, 1893)

Material. 1♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125-1310 m, N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 28.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Notes. *Trichochrysea cephalotes* is easily distinguished from its congeners in the pronotum widened anteriorly and in truncated apex of the aedeagus with a long and narrow process in the middle.

Distribution. Vietnam [Medvedev, Eroshkina, 1987; Kimoto, Gressitt, 1982], Thailand (first record).

Subfamily Galerucinae Latreille, 1802
Genus *Charaea* Baly, 1878

The oriental species of *Charaea* were recently reviewed by Bezděk [2017]. Several identification keys to *Charaea* species were compiled in various publications [Bezděk, Lee, 2014; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Nguyen et al., 2021, etc.].

Charaea khuntanensis sp. n.
(Figs 1, 17, 18)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 22.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Description. Male, holotype. Upperside of body entirely metallic blue; antennae, legs and underside of body dark blue; labrum black; abdomen and pygidium entirely yellow. Body length 6.2 mm. General view as in Fig. 1.

Body oblong, convex, slightly broadened posteriorly, about 1.9 times as long as wide. Head lustrous. Labrum transverse, with slightly rounded lateral margins; its anterior margin entire with several thin pale setae. Anterior margin of frontoclypeus straight with several long setae. Penultimate maxillary palpomere slightly expanded; apical palpomere moderately long, slightly narrower than previous one, conical with blunted triangular apex. Interantennal space rather wide, about 1.5 times narrower than interocular space, slightly convex medially, forming low keel. Genae short, about 5 times shorter than transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles slightly convex, rectangular with very slightly produced inner anterior angles, located widely and separated by rather wide depression; distinctly delimited posteriorly by thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles uneven, lustrous. Eyes convex, not large, slightly oval (1.19 times as long as wide); interocular space about twice wider than transverse diameter of eye. Vertex convex, slightly depressed medially, with thin longitudinal groove in middle; surface of vertex sparsely distinctly punctured and with microsculpture. Antennae rather robust, about 1.6 times as short as body length. Antennomere I moderately large, widened at apex; antennomere II shortest, almost cylindrical. Antennomeres III–X slightly widened at apex. Last antennomere cylindrical for most of length then narrows towards sharp apex. Antennomeres IV–XI matte, covered with sparse long semi-erect and denser short semi-adpressed setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 16 : 9 : 13 : 12 : 13 : 13 : 14 : 14 : 14 : 13 : 21, width ratio as 7 : 5 : 5 : 6 : 6.5 : 7 : 7 : 8 : 7 : 7 : 6.

Pronotum transverse, about 1.5 times as wide as long; at level of its posterior angles 1.35 times narrower than elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin almost straight, slightly notched before anterior angles; posterior margin oblique from posterior angles to almost straight central portion; lateral margins rather widely and unevenly rounded (widest at anterior third), barely noticeable notched before anterior angles. Anterior and posterior margins thinly bordered, lateral margins widely bordered. Anterior angles slightly blunted and protruding; posterior angles obtuse, slightly protruding. Anterior and posterior angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta, lateral margin with several additional short setae along entire length. Pronotal surface rather strongly convex, lustrous, densely covered with distinct punctures of varying sizes.

Scutellum slightly transverse, triangular, with blunted apex, about 1.3 times as wide as long; its surface lustrous, without punctures but with fine microsculpture. Elytra about 1.6 times as long as wide, slightly widened behind middle; its apex widely rounded. Elytra with very weak sub-basal depression. Elytral surface densely and confusedly punctured with distinct punctures; interstices flat along suture, slightly convex in middle and wrinkled laterally. Humeral calli developed. Epipleura wide at base, then gradually narrowing and disappearing before apex. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate with rare semi-erect setae. Macropterous.

Legs robust, moderately densely covered with semi-erect setae. All tibiae with short apical spurs. Pro- and mesotarsomere I rectangular, with convex upper surface, slightly enlarged, but narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 11 : 11 : 8 : 19; width ratio of protarsomeres I–III as 8 : 7 : 11. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 13 : 11 :

Figs 1–4. Species of the subfamily Galerucinae from Thailand, general view.

1 – *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n., male, holotype; 2 – *Atysa brevicornis*, male; 3 – *Paridea glyphea*, male; 4 – *Japonitata insolita* sp. n., male, holotype.

Рис. 1–4. Виды подсемейства Galerucinae из Таиланда, габитус.

1 – *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n., самец, голотип; 2 – *Atysa brevicornis*, самец; 3 – *Paridea glyphea*, самец; 4 – *Japonitata insolita* sp. n., самец, ГОЛОТИП.

Figs 5–8. Species of the subfamily Galerucinae, section Monoleptites, general view.
 5 – *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n., male, holotype (Thailand); 6 – *M. quadrifoveolata* sp. n., male, holotype (Vietnam); 7 – *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n., male, holotype (Vietnam); 8 – *P. rubricollis*, male, holotype (Vietnam).

Рис. 5–8. Виды подсемейства Galerucinae, секции Monoleptites, габитус.

5 – *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n., самец, голотип (Таиланд); 6 – *M. quadrifoveolata* sp. n., самец, голотип (Вьетнам); 7 – *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n., самец, голотип (Вьетнам); 8 – *P. rubricollis*, самец, голотип (Вьетнам).

7 : 19; width ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III as 7 : 6 : 11. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 15 : 11 : 8 : 19; width ratio of metatarsomeres I–III as 6.5 : 6 : 10. Metatarsomere I relatively long, more or less rectangular, not enlarged, about 1.9 times as short as next three tarsomeres combined. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Prosternal process very narrow, almost not visible between procoxae. Procoxal cavities open posteriorly. Abdomen with 5 distinctly visible ventrites; last one trilobed, middle lobe more or less rectangular with slightly rounded distal angles and almost straight apical margin. Pygidium convex with widely rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 17, 18) about 4 times as long as wide, with narrow triangular apex. Ventral side of aedeagus convex with thin groove in apical portion. Aedeagus sinuous in lateral view, with slightly curved down tip. Length of aedeagus about 1.7 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n. differs from other congeners in the structure of the aedeagus with narrow triangular apex and in the larger body. In the key of *Charaea* species given by Bezděk [2017], *Ch. khuntanensis* sp. n. should be placed near *Ch. pytlaki* Bezděk, 2017. The latter also has the aedeagus with triangular apex, but differs in the smaller body, the more convex pronotum, the somewhat wider aedeagus with thinner apical portion in lateral view and in brown antennae with robust last four antennomeres (1.5–1.6 times as long as wide). *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n. has the narrow aedeagus with comparatively thicker apical portion and hook-shaped bent downwards tip in lateral view, the less convex pronotum, the large body (6.2 mm) and black antennae with less robust last four antennomeres (about 2 times as long as wide). *Charaea shirozui* (Kimoto, 1969) and *C. parvicollis* (Wiese, 1889) from China also have the narrow aedeagus with sharp apex, but the first one has the aedeagus strongly bent down in preapical portion; the latter species differs in the fine puncturation of the pronotum and elytra, dark-brown or black antennae and legs as well as the thin aedeagus in lateral view. Moreover, both these species have relatively short body (less 5 mm).

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to the collecting locality situated on the Khun Tan Range.

Genus *Apophyllia* Thomson, 1858

Apophyllia borowieci Bezděk, 2004

Material. 3♂ (PR), "LAO: Phongsaly prov., 20°41'2" N 102°6'8' E, 1100 m, 28.v.–20.vi.2003, Phongsaly evn., ~1500 m, Pacholátka leg."; 1♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 28.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Notes. This species is easily distinguished from congeneric species in having of dents on protarsomere I and mesotarsomere I. A specimen of this species from Thailand is very similar to ones from Laos, but has slightly larger dents on pro- and metatarsomere I.

Distribution. Laos [Bezděk, 2004, 2008], Thailand (first record).

Apophyllia clypeata Samoderzhenkov, 1988

Type material. 1♂, paratype (ZIN); "Vietnam – Gia Lai, Son Lang, 40 km N Akhe, 25.XI–4.VII.1978, 700 m, L. Medvedev leg."; 1♀, paratype (ZIN), "SRV, Pro. Gialai-Contum, Buon-Loi, 40 km N Akhe, 10.VI.1980"

Material. 1♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 28.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Distribution. Vietnam, Laos [Bezděk, 2005], Thailand (first record).

Genus *Atysa* Baly, 1864

Oriental species of *Atysa* were reviewed and keyed by Medvedev [2005a]. In addition, several identification keys to *Atysa* species were compiled [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963; Kimoto, 1989; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015].

Atysa brevicornis (Samoderzhenkov, 1988)

(Fig. 2, 31, 32)

Type material. 1♀, holotype (ZIN), "BETHAM горы в верховьях HAM-MA, 1000 м. у ДОИГ-ПАО 28.V.1963 OK" (VIETNAM mountains in the upper reaches of the NAM-MA, 1000 m near DONG-PAO); 1♀, paratype (ZIN), "BETHAM горы у ШАПА, 2000 м 2.6.1963 Кабаков" (VIETNAM mountains near SHAPA, 2000 m Kabakov).

Material. 2♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1108 m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" N 18°57'1", E 99°21'8.4" 21.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1105-1186 m N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" N 18°56'49", E 99°21'01" 22.V.2025"; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1285-1525 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'17.4", E 99°23'9.9" 23.V.2025"

Notes. This species was known only from females. It is characterized by sexual dimorphism: males have longer and somewhat less expanded antennomeres III–VI than females. The photographs of the habitus of male (Fig. 2) and aedeagus (Figs 31, 32) are given for the first time.

Distribution. Vietnam, Laos [Medvedev, 2005a], Thailand (first record).

Atysa gressitti (L. Medvedev, 2005)

Material. 1♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1285-1458 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'10", E 99°22'47" 20.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Distribution. China (Fujian, Zhejiang) [Medvedev, 2005a; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015], Thailand (first record).

Genus *Paridea* Baly, 1886

Paridea (Semacia) glyphea Yang, 1993

(Fig. 3)

Material. 1♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1246 m N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" – N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg."

Notes. This species was known only by the holotype. *Paridea glyphea* is easily distinguished from all congeners in male elytra expanded in middle of lateral margins and in the presence of cavities on the elytral surface (Fig. 3).

Distribution. China (Yunnan), [Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Beenen, 2024], Thailand (first record).

Genus *Japonitata* Strand, 1935

Japonitata comprises more than 30 species in the Oriental and Palaearctic regions with the majority of species (60%) described from China [Lee, 2022]. This genus is similar to *Paraplotes* Laboissière, 1933 but differs in the pronotum with unbordered posterior margin and in procoxal cavities open posteriorly. The composition of both genera is not stable in the literature and transfers between both genera are expected. Among the most important papers, identification keys to Oriental and Chinese *Japonitata* species are worth mentioning [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963; Chen, Jiang, 1986; Kimoto, 1989; Jiang, 1989; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Lee, 2022].

Japonitata insolita sp. n.
(Figs 4, 19, 20, 43)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 29.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Description. Male, holotype. Antennae black, with slightly paler first and last antennomeres. Head black. Pronotum pale brown. Elytra black. Legs black with paler profemora and protibiae. Ventral side of body black with abdomen brown. Body length 3.5 mm. General view as in Fig. 4.

Body rather oblong, about 1.84 times as long as wide, widest approximately before apical slope of elytra. Head lustrous, labrum transverse with convex apical margin. Labrum surface slightly convex, impunctate and lustrous. Penultimate maxillary palpomere strongly expanded; apical palpomere short, conical. Frontoclypeus convex, impunctate and lustrous with indistinct, slightly convex ridge in interantennal space. Genae short, about 4 times as short as transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles moderately convex, triangular, with slightly produced inner anterior angles, located closely and almost touching each other with their inner sides but distinct separated by thin deep groove, distinctly delimited posteriorly by thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles impunctate, lustrous. Eyes small, oval (1.25 times as long as wide); interocular space about 2 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex convex and lustrous, without punctures or depression. Antennae (Fig. 43) rather long, 1.35 times as short as body length. Antennomere I not large, club-shaped, widened at apex; antennomere II shortest, slightly widened before apex. Antennomeres III–VII slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres VIII–IX more or less cylindrical, the latter with two-three (2 on left antenna, 3 on right one) long, thin, slightly expanded at apex, ciliate-like processes on outer apical margin. Antennomere X with cylindrical, truncated at apex process at outer apical margin. Last antennomere spindle-shaped with sharp tip; noticeably narrower than antennomeres VIII or IX and slightly narrower than one X. All antennomeres not densely covered with short semi-addressed setae and with separate protruding setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 14 : 5 : 11 : 10 : 9 : 9 : 10 : 8 : 10 : 7.5 : 15, width ratio as 4 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 4 : 5 : 6 : 6 : 4 : 3.5.

Pronotum transverse, about 2.2 times as wide as long (widest anteriorly); at level of its posterior angles about 1.7 times as narrow as elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin slightly concave; posterior slightly convex but slightly notched before posterior angles; lateral margins almost straight. Anterior and posterior margins unbordered, lateral margins distinctly bordered. Anterior angles blunted; posterior angles obtuse, not protruding. Pronotal surface lustrous and impunctate, slightly transversely depressed along middle.

Scutellum triangular, with sharp apex, with subequal width and length; its surface lustrous without punctures. Elytra 1.34 times as long as wide; widened before apical slope; its apex widely rounded. Elytra with two ridges starting from humerus: first ridge along lateral margin, ending approximately at level of middle of apical slope; second one curved, running on elytral surface ending before apical slope. Elytral surface sparsely and confusedly punctured, with distinct small punctures; interstices convex, wrinkled in places; with several sparse setae on apical slope. Humeral calli well developed. Epipleura wide at base, then gradually narrowing and disappearing before apex. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate, slightly longitudinally depressed. Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, sparsely covered with semi-erect setae. Pro- and mesotibiae straight, metatibiae slightly curved; all tibiae without spurs. Tarsomere I of all legs not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 9 : 5 : 5 : 8. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 11 : 6 : 5 : 10. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 15 : 6 : 5 : 9. Metatarsomere I almost straight, about as long as next three

tarsomeres combined and about 3.6 times as short as length of tibia. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side sparsely covered with adpressed setae and small punctures. Prosternal process reduced to very narrow keel, not visible between coxae. Procoxal cavities open posteriorly. Abdomen deformed (at least in the holotype). Pygidium convex, triangular, with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 19, 20) wide in basal portion, with maximum width 0.2 mm, then narrowing with minimal width 0.1–0.13 at level of apical quarter (accurate measurement impossible because of incomplete sclerotization in this place), then slightly widening again (with width 0.15 mm before apex). Apex of aedeagus triangular, with slightly rounded tip. In lateral view, aedeagus slightly curved. Ventral side of aedeagus convex. Length of aedeagus about 1.35 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Japonitata insolita* sp. n. belongs to the species group with modified apical antennomeres and two ridges on elytra. This group includes also *J. abdominalis* Jiang, 1989, *J. antennata* Chen et Jiang, 1986 and *J. hongpingana* Jiang, 1989. But *J. abdominalis* is easily distinguished from all other group members in the triangular process on the outside of the antennomere IX (other species of this group have the process on the antennomere X). *Japonitata insolita* sp. n. can be easily distinguished from *J. antennata* and *J. hongpingana* in the antennomere IX with two-three long and thin slightly expanded at apex ciliate-like processes on the outer apical margin, in the antennomere X with a cylindrical, truncated at apex process at the outer apical margin and in the comparatively narrow last antennomere, which is noticeably narrower than previous three antennomeres combined (Fig. 43); instead of the antennomere IX without ciliate-like processes, the transverse antennomere X with a sharp triangular process on the outer apical margin and the widest last antennomere in *J. antennata* and *J. hongpingana*.

Japonitata insolita sp. n. is also similar to some species of the genus *Paraplotes*, especially ones having modified antennae (*P. antennalis* Chen, 1942 and *P. clavicornis* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963). But the former is easily distinguished from it in the very large and long antennomere XI which is longer than the antennomeres VIII–X combined. The latter differs from the new species in antennae with expanded apical antennomeres, which are as wide as long.

Etymology. The name of this new species refers to the unusual shape of its antennae.

Genus *Monolepta* Chevrolat, 1836

Monolepta is the most speciose galerucine genus, with more 700 described nominal species, occurs mainly in tropical and subtropical regions. There are many articles devoted to the systematics of the genus *Monolepta*. Among the most important papers identification keys to Oriental and Chinese *Monolepta* species are worth mentioning [Maulik, 1936; Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963; Kimoto, 1989; Mohamedsaid, 1993; Medvedev, 2005b; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Lei et al., 2021; Hazmi, Wagner, 2022].

Monolepta trizonalis sp. n.
(Figs 5, 23, 24, 46)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 26.V.2025

P. Romantsov leg. Paratypes: 1♀ (ZIN), the same locality and collector, but "1226-1400 m N 18°56'31", E 99°21'28" N 18°56'20", E 99°22'28" 23.V.2024"; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1125-1310 m, N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" N 18°56'54", E 99°22'28" 28.V.2025".

Description. Male, holotype. Antennae, head and legs brown. Pronotum brown with blurred, indistinct, whitish areas. Elytra black at basal third and red at apical third, with wide yellow band (widest laterally and narrowing towards suture) between them. Epipleura black at basal portion, reddish in middle portion and red at apical third. Ventral side with proventrite light brown, meso- and metaventrites black and abdominal ventrites reddish. Body length 5 mm. General view as in Fig. 5.

Body rather oblong, about 2 times as long as wide, widest slightly behind middle. Head lustrous, labrum with convex apical margin. Labrum surface convex, impunctate, lustrous, with several setae along apical margin. Penultimate maxillary palpomere not expanded; apical palpomere moderately long, not narrower than previous one, conical, with sharp tip. Frontoclypeus slightly convex, impunctate, lustrous, with slightly convex, indistinct ridge in interantennal space. Genae short, about 5 times short as transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles moderately convex, triangular, with distinctly produced inner anterior angles, located closely and almost touching each other with their inner sides but distinctly separated by thin deep groove, distinctly delimited posteriorly by thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles impunctate, lustrous. Eyes large, slightly oval (1.1 times as long as wide); interocular space about as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex convex, without longitudinal groove in middle or depression before frontal tubercles; surface of vertex sparsely covered with very small, microscopic punctures. Antennae long, slightly longer than body length, filiform. Antennomere I moderately large, club-shaped, slightly widened at apex; antennomere II shortest, slightly widened before apex. Antennomeres III–V slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres VI–X almost cylindrical. Last antennomere slightly widened in anterior quarter, then narrows towards sharp apex. Antennomeres I–III almost glabrous, other ones not densely covered with short semi-adpressed and with sparse longer semi-erect setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 20 : 8 : 9 : 22 : 20 : 20 : 20 : 18 : 17 : 20, width ratio as 5 : 4 : 4 : 5 : 5 : 4 : 4 : 4 : 4 : 4 : 4.

Pronotum transverse, about 1.8 times as wide as long (widest at anterior third); at level of its posterior angles 1.43 times as narrow as elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin slightly concave; posterior margin bevelled from posterior angles to almost straight central part; lateral margins rather widely rounded, barely noticeable notched before anterior angles. Anterior margin unbordered, lateral margins widely bordered; posterior margin distinctly bordered near posterior angles but not bordered opposite of scutellum. Anterior angles blunted; posterior angles obtuse, almost not protruding. Anterior and posterior angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta, lateral margin with several additional short setae. Pronotal surface convex, lustrous, sparsely covered with very small, microscopic punctures.

Scutellum narrowly triangular with sharp apex, about 0.8 times as wide as long; its surface lustrous without punctures. Elytra 1.52 times as long as wide; slightly widened behind middle; its apex rounded. Elytra without sub-basal depression or modified area. Elytral surface sparsely and confusedly punctured with distinct small punctures; interstices flat, covered with microsculpture. Humeral calli developed. Epipleura wide at anterior third, then gradually narrowing and disappearing at level of metacoxae. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate. Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, sparsely covered with semi-erect setae. Protibiae slightly curved with short spur, mesotibiae straight with very short spur, metatibiae curved with long spur. Protarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than protarsomere III. Meso- and metatarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 10 : 5 : 8 : 13; width ratio of protarsomeres I–III as 5.5 : 4 : 10. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 11 : 5 : 6 : 14;

width ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III as 4 : 5 : 10. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 30 : 5.5 : 6 : 12; width ratio of metatarsomeres I–III as 5 : 5 : 8. Metatarsomere I distinctly curved in basal third, about 1.5 times as long as next three tarsomeres combined and about 2.1 times shorter than length of tibia. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side sparsely covered with adpressed setae and small punctures. Prosternal process reduced to very narrow keel not visible between procoxae. Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite trilobed; middle lobe rectangular with almost straight apical margin, longer than lateral lobes, its surface widely and shallowly depressed in middle. Pygidium convex, triangular with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 23, 24) wide in basal half (with maximum width 0.42 mm), then narrowing and passing into narrow apical process almost parallel-sided in last third (with minimal width before apex 0.07 mm). Apex of aedeagus blunted and slightly rounded. Aedeagus sinuous in lateral view. Ventral side of aedeagus convex in basal part, with two longitudinal keels before passing to apical process. The latter longitudinally depressed along entire length. Length of aedeagus about 2.05 mm.

Females are similar to male in body colouration, but last abdominal ventrite simple. Spermatheca as in Fig. 46. Length of spermatheca 0.37 mm. Body length 5.6–5.7 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n. belongs to the species group with the brown pronotum and tricoloured (black, red and yellow) elytra. This group includes also *M. orientalis* Jacoby, 1889 and *M. zonalis* Gressitt et Kimoto, 1963, but they both differ from the new species in the elytra colouration consisting of several bands: four bands in *M. orientalis* and six ones in *M. zonalis*. *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n. has a unique elytral colouration which consists of three multi-colour zones well separated from each other. In addition, the new species differs from other two members of this group in the shape of the aedeagus with wide basal portion and narrow apical process. *Monolepta orientalis* and *M. zonalis* have the aedeagus rather wide, only slightly narrowing to the apex, without a pronounced apical process. *Monolepta bakoensis* L. Medvedev, 2015, also having tricoloured elytra, is similar to members of this group, but it is easily distinguished from them in the head and the pronotum black. All other *Monolepta* have unicoloured or bicoloured elytra.

Etymology. The name of this new species refers to its colouration with three different coloured zones on elytra.

Monolepta quadrifoveolata sp. n.

(Figs 6, 21, 22)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): "N Vietnam, Hòa Bình Prov., Mai Chau Vill., Eco Homestay, N 20°38'56.6", E 105°3'59.2, 170 m, at light, 22.IV.2019 P. Romantsov leg."

Description. Male, holotype. Antennae brown, with 2 basal antennomeres paler. Head brown, with frontal tubercles and vertex dark brown. Pronotum red brown; scutellum brown; elytra red brown, with large pale yellow oblong spot on each elytron occupying almost two-thirds of its surface and leaving only narrow edging of lateral and apical margins brown. Intensity of elytral colouration not uniform: maximal colouration around postscutellar depression (bright red on sides of it and almost white behind it). Underside of body brown, with metathorax slightly darker. Legs brown with pro- and mesotarsi darkened. Metatarsi brown, with base of metatarsomere I narrowly blackened. Body length 5.5 mm. General view as in Fig. 6.

Body not very elongate, about 1.8 times as long as wide, widest behind middle. Head lustrous, labrum transverse (about 2.3 times

as wide as long) with almost straight apical margin. Labrum surface slightly convex, impunctate with one long seta near each posterior angle. Penultimate maxillary palpomere slightly expanded; apical palpomere conical with sharp tip. Frontoclypeus rather narrow and convex, almost impunctate, forming low but distinct ridge in interantennal space. Genae very short, about 7.5 times as short as transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles moderately convex, triangular, with distinctly produced inner anterior angles; located closely and almost touching each other with their inner sides but distinct separated by thin groove, not delimited anteriorly (connected with interantennal ridge), delimited posteriorly with thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles lustrous and impunctate. Eyes very large and convex, oval (about 1.3 times as long as wide); interocular space about 1.1 times as narrow as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex convex, without depressions, covered with very small punctures and indistinct transverse microsculpture. Antennae rather long, about as long as body, filiform. Antennomere I large, slightly curved, club-shaped; antennomere II shortest, slightly widened before apex. Antennomeres III–V slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres VI–X almost cylindrical. Antennomere XI slightly constricted at level of apical third, with sharp tip. Antennomeres I–II sparsely covered with short semi-adpressed setae, other ones more densely covered with short semi-adpressed setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 23 : 7.5 : 11 : 22 : 23 : 23 : 23 : 24 : 23 : 20 : 24, width ratio as 6 : 4 : 5 : 5 : 5 : 4.5 : 4 : 4 : 3 : 3 : 3.

Pronotum transverse, about 1.5 times as wide as long, with more or less uniform width along entire length; 1.57 times as narrow at level of its posterior angles as elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin almost straight; posterior margin slightly convex; lateral margins almost straight, just very slightly notched before posterior angles. Anterior margin unbordered; posterior margin bordered only near posterior angles, lateral margins distinctly bordered. Anterior angles slightly rounded, not protruding; posterior angles acute, distinctly protruding. Pronotal surface with oblique depression on each side of middle; shagreen, with distinct punctures and slightly wrinkled interstices.

Scutellum about as wide as long, triangular, with sharp apex; its surface smooth and lustrous. Elytra about 1.4 times as long as wide; relatively narrow at base, gradually widened (widest at level of posterior third) and then somewhat more abruptly narrowed towards widely rounded apex. Each elytron with transverse postscutellar depression consisting of two deep foveae separated by high bridge. Elytral surface sparsely and confusedly covered with small distinct punctures, with flat interstices. Punctures in modified elytral area almost indistinct. Humeral calli well developed. Epipleura wide at anterior third, then rather suddenly narrowing and disappearing at level of abdominal ventrite 2. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate. Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, sparsely covered with semi-erect setae. Protibiae almost straight, mesotibiae very slightly and metatibiae stronger curved. All tibiae slightly widened at apex; pro- and mesotibiae without spurs, metatibiae with long spur at apex. Pro-, meso- and metatarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 11 : 5 : 5 : 11; of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 18 : 7 : 6 : 14; of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 40 : 8 : 5 : 12. Metatarsomere I straight, slightly widened at apex; about 2 times as long as three next tarsomeres combined and approximately twice shorter than length of tibia. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side covered with pale adpressed setae. Prosternal process reduced to very narrow keel, barely visible between coxae. Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite trilobed, middle lobe almost square, just slightly longer than lateral lobes, its surface almost flat, with small, round, shallow, barely visible depression in apical portion. Pygidium convex, triangular, with slightly rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 21, 22) rather short, about 4 times as long as wide, widest at level of apical third, then narrowing towards narrowly triangular apex in dorsal view. Aedeagus in lateral view slightly curved. Ventral side of aedeagus strongly convex, without longitudinal depression. Length of aedeagus about 1.5 mm, width 0.37 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Monolepta quadriveolata* sp. n. belongs to the group of continental *Monolepta* species having depression on the elytral surface. This new species differs from other congeners in its unusual colouration (upperside of body reddish-brown with a large pale yellow oblong spot on each elytron occupying almost two-thirds of its surface) and in an unusual shape of postscutellar depression on the elytral surface in male. The majority of other species of this group have elytra with elongate depressions (spindle- or comma-shaped). *Monolepta quadriveolata* sp. n. has a transverse postscutellar depression on each elytron consisting of two deep foveae separated by a high partition. This new species has a double depression (consisting of two depressions) on each elytron and the aedeagus widened before triangular apex, most similar to those in *M. bicavipennis* Chen, 1942 and *M. quadricavata* Chen, 1976 from China. The first compared species has one depression on the each elytron and the black pronotum, and the latter one has upperside of body completely brown and elongate depressions on the elytra. Other continental species of this group (*M. cavipennis* Baly, 1878, *M. discoidalis* (Jacoby, 1895), *M. marginipennis* (Jacoby, 1892), *M. scutellaris* Kimoto, 1989, *M. vietnamica* Kimoto, 1989) differ from the new species in the elytra with black pattern and different shape of a postscutellar depression on the the elytra.

Paleosepharia gongshana Chen et Jiang, 1986 having a similar body colouration is also similar to this new species but can be easily distinguished in rounded lateral margins of the pronotum and elongate spindle-shaped postscutellar depression on the elytral surface. *Monolepta quadriveolata* sp. n. has almost straight lateral margins of the pronotum and transverse postscutellar depression on the elytra.

Notes. Feng et al. [2025] transferred *M. bicavipennis* and *M. quadricavata* to *Paleosepharia* Laboissière, 1936. However, these species do not fully correspond to the characteristics of the genus *Paleosepharia* given by these authors [Feng et al., 2025: 33]: “the third antennomere is longer than the second, the epipleuron continues towards the apex, the aedeagus is parallel-sided in the basal two-thirds, apical third strongly narrowed”. They have the aedeagus widened before apex and epipleura not reaching apex of elytra. In addition, these two species have rounded apices of elytra what is a generally accepted the character of *Monolepta* (instead of truncated ones in *Paleosepharia*). In my opinion the question on the difference between these two genera still remains open and requires further study.

The syntypes of *M. bicavipennis*, *M. cavipennis*, *M. discoidalis* and *M. marginipennis* were studied based on photographs kindly provided by Jan Bezděk. The photographs of the syntypes of *M. bicavipennis* and *M. quadricavata* were published by Feng et al. [2025].

Etymology. The name of this new species refers to its elytra with four foveae.

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Figs 9–12. Species of the subfamily Galerucinae, general view.
 9 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., male, holotype (Thailand); 10 – *Philopona shima*, female (Thailand); 11 – *Eudolia birmanica*, male, paratype (Myanmar); 12 – *E. doisaketensis* sp. n., male, holotype (Thailand).

Рис. 9–12. Виды подсемейства Galerucinae, габитус.

9 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., самец, голотип (Таиланд); 10 – *Philopona shima*, самка (Таиланд); 11 – *Eudolia birmanica*, самец, паратип (Мьянма); 12 – *E. doisaketensis* sp. n., самец, голотип (Таиланд).

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Figs 13–16. Species of the subfamily Galerucinae, tribe Alticini, general view.

13 – *Phygasia pseudomedia*, male, holotype (China); 14 – *P. oblongomaculata* sp. n., male, holotype (Thailand); 15 – *P. vietnamica*, male, holotype (Vietnam); 16 – *Yunotrichia mediovittata*, female (Thailand).

Рис. 13–16. Виды подсемейства Galerucinae, трибы Alticini, рабитуc.

13 – *Phygasia pseudomedia*, самец, голотип (Китай); 14 – *P. oblongomaculata* sp. n., самец, голотип (Таиланд); 15 – *P. vietnamica*, самец, голотип (Вьетнам); 16 – *Yunotrichia mediovittata*, самка (Таиланд).

Genus *Paleosepharia* Laboissière, 1936

There are many papers devoted to the systematics of the genus *Paleosepharia*. Species of this genus from Indochina were reviewed and keyed by Medvedev [2014]. In addition, some identification keys to *Paleosepharia* species were compiled [Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963; Kimoto, 1989; Mohamedsaid, 1996; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Lee, 2018; Feng et al., 2025]. In addition, the work of Mohamedsaid and Furth [2011] about secondary sexual characters in males of Galerucinae, which includes this genus, deserves special mention. Several recently published works provide descriptions of new species and new records, as well as taxonomic remarks to already known species from the region under consideration [Mohamedsaid, Constant, 2007; Medvedev, 2013; Rizki et al., 2014, 2016; Nguyen, Gómez-Zurita, 2017, etc.].

Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis sp. n. (Figs 7, 25, 26)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): "N Vietnam, Lao Cai Prov., near Sa Pa, Chapi Homestay N 22°19'52.3", E 103°49'45.2" 1285 m., 14.V.2018 P. Romantsov leg."

Description. Male, holotype. Antennae brown, with antennomeres III–XI darkened. Head brown, pronotum and scutellum light brown, elytra black, with pale brown postscutellar depression and large, very pale (almost white) spot on each elytron, underside of body brown, pygidium brown with pale apex; legs brown with tibiae and tarsi darkened. Body length 5.8 mm. General view as in Fig. 7.

Body not very elongate, about 1.8 times as long as wide, widest behind middle. Head lustrous, labrum with almost straight apical margin. Labrum surface slightly convex, impunctate, lustrous with several long setae along apical and basal margins. Penultimate maxillary palpomere slightly expanded; apical palpomere rather long (as long as previous one), conical with sharp tip. Frontoclypeus wide and convex, almost impunctate, forming distinct ridge in interantennal space. Genae very short, about 7.5 times shorter than transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles moderately convex, subquadrate, with slightly produced inner anterior angles; located closely and almost touching each other with their inner sides but distinct separated by thin groove, not delimited anteriorly (connected with interantennal ridge), delimited posteriorly with thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles covered with fine microsculpture. Eyes large, convex, oval (1.25 times as long as wide); interocular space about as wide as diameter of eye. Vertex convex, with barely noticeable trace of longitudinal groove in middle and with very small depression before frontal tubercles; vertex surface covered with indistinct microsculpture. Antennae rather long, 1.05 times shorter than body length, filiform. Antennomere I large, slightly curved, club-shaped; antennomere II shortest, slightly widened before apex. Antennomeres III–V slightly widened at apex. Antennomeres VI–X almost cylindrical. Antennomere XI slightly constricted before apex with sharp tip. Antennomeres I–II sparsely covered with short semi-adpressed setae, other ones more densely covered with short semi-adpressed setae and with separate protruding setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 28 : 7 : 9 : 15 : 24 : 26 : 22 : 25 : 24 : 25 : 25, width ratio as 7 : 4 : 4 : 5 : 5 : 4.5 : 4 : 4 : 3 : 3 : 3.

Pronotum transverse, about 1.7 times as wide as long (widest at anterior third); at level of its posterior angles about 1.4 times as narrow as elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin almost straight; posterior margin slightly convex; lateral margins slightly sinuous, slightly notched before anterior and posterior angles. Anterior margin unbordered; posterior margin very thinly

bordered, lateral margins distinctly bordered. Anterior angles almost rectangular, slightly protruding; posterior angles obtuse, slightly protruding. Anterior and posterior angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta. Pronotal surface lustrous with sparse, small punctures on sides and larger ones in middle; without traces of any depressions.

Scutellum slightly transverse (about 1.15 times as wide as long), triangular with sharp apex; its surface lustrous with very small punctures and microsculpture. Elytra 1.44 times as long as wide; relatively narrow at base, gradually widened (widest at level of posterior third) and then more abruptly narrowed towards sharply truncated apex. Each elytron with elongate, slightly obliquely outward posteriorly depression behind scutellum. Almost all elytral surface sparsely and confusedly punctured with very small punctures, with wide, flat interstices. Punctures in modified elytral area almost indistinct. Humeral calli developed. Epipleura moderately wide at anterior quarter, then gradually narrowing toward truncated apex and disappearing near outer elytral angles. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate, concave (slightly in basal and deeper in apical halves). Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, sparsely covered with semi-erect setae. Protibiae almost straight, mesotibiae slightly and metatibiae strongly curved. All tibiae very slightly widened at apex, pro- and mesotibiae without spurs, metatibiae with long spur. Pro-, meso- and metatarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 16 : 9 : 7 : 14; of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 23 : 8 : 6.5 : 15; of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 47 : 10 : 7 : 12. Metatarsomere I straight with almost parallel margins; about 1.8 times as long as three next tarsomeres combined and approximately twice shorter than length of tibia. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side covered with pale adpressed setae. Prosternal process reduced to very narrow keel barely visible between coxae. Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite trilobed, middle lobe rectangular slightly longer than lateral lobes, its surface with wide longitudinal triangular depression along entire length (narrow in basal part and expanding towards apex). Pygidium convex, more or less trapezoidal; its apex with wide triangular notch in middle.

Aedeagus (Figs 25, 26) very long, moderately wide in basal half (with maximum width 0.37 mm), then narrowing towards apex (with minimal width before apex 0.075 mm). Apex of aedeagus truncate in dorsal view. Aedeagus in lateral view sinuous and strongly bent down (at angle almost 90°) before apex. Ventral side of aedeagus convex in basal half and with longitudinal depression in other visible part. Length of aedeagus about 2.5 mm, width 0.37 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n. differs from other congeners in its colouration: the head is brown, the pronotum and scutellum are light brown, the elytra is black with a postscutellar depression brown and a large light-pale (almost white) spot on each elytron, the underside of the body is brown, the pygidium is brown with pale apex; in the long and thin aedeagus with very elongate apical portion, which is strongly curved down in lateral view; as well as in the unusual shape of a modified area on the male elytra. *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n. is the most similar to *P. rubricollis* L. Medvedev, 2009 from Vietnam, which has a very similar body colouration (Fig. 8). The latter differs from the new species in the aedeagus (Figs 27, 28) with less elongate apical portion which is just very slightly curved in lateral view, as well as in a smaller modified area in the male elytra. In addition, it has a sharp tip of the aedeagus instead of truncated one in *P. pseudorubicollis* sp. n.

This new species is also similar to *P. fasciata* Kimoto, 1963 from China, but the latter has the trapezoidal pronotum

and the distinctly punctured, not modified elytra with narrower yellow band. *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n. has the pronotum more rounded at sides and the indistinctly punctured elytra with a distinct and rather deep modified area behind suture and a large pale spot on each elytron.

Etymology. The name of this new species indicates its similarity to *P. rubricollis*.

Paleosepharia magnitarsis Romantsov, 2025

Type material. 1♂, holotype (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105 m, at light N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" 26.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg."

Material. 1♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 20.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Notes. Until now, the species has been known only by the holotype. Another male of this rare species was found in the material collected by author in 2025 in the type locality. The latter specimen resembles the holotype in almost all characters except the body length 6 mm (instead of 6.1 mm in the holotype).

Distribution. Thailand.

Genus *Sinoluperoides* Kimoto, 1989

Sinoluperoides chenchirae Romantsov, 2025

(Fig. 50)

Type material. 1♂, holotype (ZIN), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1288-1246 m, N 18°56'46", E 99°21'2" – N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 14.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg."; 1♂, paratype (PR), the same locality and collector as in the holotype, but "h~1105-1099 m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" – N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 13.V.2024".

Material. 1♂ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1402 m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'39", E 99°22'35" 18.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 19.V.2025"; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 26.V.2025".

Notes. This species was known only by males. In 2025 two females were collected in the type locality. One of them is similar to male, but has a somewhat paler body colouration (the pronotum completely brown, the elytra with basal area brown) and the body length 3.7 mm. The second female has the dark brown head, the pronotum and legs completely black, the body length 5.2 mm. Females have antennae shorter than male and not modified metatibiae. The photograph of the spermatheca (Fig. 50) is given for the first time.

Distribution. Thailand.

Genus *Strobiderus* Jacoby, 1884

The leaf beetle genus *Strobiderus* comprises 22 species (not counting a new species described in this paper) occurring in the Oriental and Afrotropic regions [Berti, 1986; Medvedev, Beneen, 2010]. *Strobiderus* is classified in the section *Doryscites* within the tribe Luperini together with the genera *Doryscus* Jacoby, 1887 and *Trichobalya* Weise, 1924 [Wilcox, 1973]. Members of the genus *Strobiderus* can be distinguished from the other two genera in following characters: simple (not enlarged) posterior claws (enlarged in *Doryscus*); the pronotum without distinct impressions; the elytra with simple (not double) rows of punctures (double in *Trichobalya*) or with entirely confused puncturation; the

aedeagus in form long, thin tube with a very long, filament-like apical process (wider with not separated apical process in the other two genera). The elytra are usually covered with long erect or adpressed setae, sometimes with only adpressed setae or almost glabrous. The oriental species of this genus were comparatively recently reviewed and keyed by Medvedev and Beneen [2010].

Strobiderus excavatipennis sp. n.

(Figs 9, 29, 30, 42, 47, 48)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (PR): "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 19.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg.". Paratypes: 2♀ (PR, ZIN), the same locality and collector as in the holotype, but "h~1105-1099 m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" – N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 13.V.2024"; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but "h~1105 m, at light N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" 14.V.2024"; 2♀ (PR), the same data as in the holotype, but "27.V.2025".

Description. Male, holotype. Head black, with labrum yellow and vertex brown; pronotum brown, with dark brown area along anterior margin; elytra pale brown. Antennae and legs pale brown. Ventral side of body pale brown, with proventrite brown. Body length 4.2 mm. General view as in Fig. 9.

Body oblong, widest before apex, about 2 times as long as wide. Head almost impunctate, labrum trapezoidal, with rounded anterior margin. Labrum convex, lustrous, impunctate but with indistinct microsculpture and several setae along margins. Penultimate maxillary palpomere slightly swollen, apical palpomere rather large and long, conical. Frontoclypeus trapezoidal, with several setae along lateral margins; almost flat, with very narrow, low, indistinct keel between eyes. Genae rather short, about 3 times as short as transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles slightly convex, transverse, with slightly produced inner anterior angles, located closely and almost touching each other with their inner sides but distinct separated by thin groove, not very distinctly delimited posteriorly. Surface of frontal tubercles shining, impunctate, but with very fine microsculpture. Eyes large, convex, oval (1.25 times as long as wide); interocular space about as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex with fine microsculpture, covered with curved seta near eye on each side. Antennae filiform. Antennomere I long, widened at apex, rest antennomeres straight, cylindrical. Antennomere XI missing. Antennomeres I and II with several setae near apex, antennomeres III–X with denser setae all over surface. Length ratio of antennomeres I–X as 25 : 6 : 13 : 25 : 20 : 18 : 18 : 17 : 14 : 12, width ratio as 5 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3 : 3.

Pronotum transverse, 1.65 times as wide as long (widest at anterior half); at level of its posterior angles about 1.5 times as narrow as elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin almost straight; posterior margin very slightly convex; lateral margins convex, slightly notched before posterior angles. Anterior margin unbordered, lateral and posterior margins bordered. Anterior angles obtuse-angled, slightly protruding with sharp tip opposite setigerous pore; posterior angles obtuse, slightly protruding. All angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta. Several additional short setae placed on lateral margin. Pronotal surface moderately lustrous, punctured with sparse, very small punctures and with fine microsculpture, with shallow indistinct transverse depression in middle of anterior third.

Scutellum triangular, transverse (about 1.7 times as wide as long); surface lustrous, with sparse, small punctures. Elytra triangularly expanded at apical quarter (Figs 9, 42), 1.88 times as long as wide at level of humeral calli and 1.35 times at level of expansion. Humeral calli well developed. Each elytron with 9 regular rows (including long scutellar one) of deep punctures and rather convex interspaces, covered with quite dense, short, adpressed pubescence and with significantly sparser long setae mainly located along lateral and apical margins. Surface of each elytron with deep complex impression (Fig. 42) near suture before

Figs 17–30. Aedeagi of holotypes, species of the subfamily Galerucinae from Thailand and Vietnam.
 17–18 – *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n.; 19–20 – *Japonitata insolita* sp. n.; 21–22 – *Monolepta quadrifoveolata* sp. n.; 23–24 – *M. trizonalis* sp. n.;
 25–26 – *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n.; 27–28 – *P. rubricollis*; 29–30 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n. 17, 19, 21, 23, 25, 27, 29 – ventral view;
 18, 20, 22, 24, 26, 28, 30 – lateral view.

Рис. 17–30. Эдеагусы голотипов, виды подсемейства Galerucinae из Таиланда и Вьетнама.
 17–18 – *Charaea khuntanensis* sp. n.; 19–20 – *Japonitata insolita* sp. n.; 21–22 – *Monolepta quadrifoveolata* sp. n.; 23–24 – *M. trizonalis* sp. n.;
 25–26 – *Paleosepharia pseudorubicollis* sp. n.; 27–28 – *P. rubricollis*; 29–30 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n. 17, 19, 21, 23, 25, 27, 29 – вид снизу; 18, 20,
 22, 24, 26, 28, 30 – вид сбоку.

Figs 31–41. Aedeagi of species of the subfamily Galerucinae from Thailand and China.
 31–32 – *Atysa brevicornis*; 33–34 – *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., holotype; 35–36 – *Phygasia oblongomaculata* sp. n., holotype; 37–38 – *P. pseudomedia*, holotype; 39 – *P. media*, holotype; 40 – *P. nigricollis*, holotype; 41 – *P. parva*, holotype. 31 – dorsal view; 33, 35, 37, 39–41 – ventral view; 32, 34, 36, 38 – lateral view.

Рис. 31–41. Эдеагусы видов подсемейства Galerucinae из Таиланда и Китая.
 31–32 – *Atysa brevicornis*; 33–34 – *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., голотип; 35–36 – *Phygasia oblongomaculata* sp. n., голотип; 37–38 – *P. pseudomedia*, голотип; 39 – *P. media*, голотип; 40 – *P. nigricollis*, голотип; 41 – *P. parva*, голотип. 31 – вид сверху; 33, 35, 37, 39–41 – вид снизу; 32, 34, 36, 38 – вид сбоку.

apical slope. Elytral surface convex and glabrous before this impression and flattened behind it. Elytral rows I–V ended before this convexity, punctures of rows VI–IX disappearing on apical slope. Lateral margin of each elytron flattened and triangularly expanded approximately at level of this impression. Epipleura narrow at base, gradually narrowing apically and disappearing at level of metacoxae. Epipleural surface impunctate and glabrous. Macropterous.

Legs long and slender, covered with pale semi-erect setae. All tibiae with spurs, longest on metatibiae. Protibiae straight, meso- and metatibiae very slightly curved. All tarsi narrow, with almost cylindrical tarsomeres. Tarsomere I of all legs not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 12 : 6 : 5 : 7; of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 21 : 6 : 5 : 7; of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 27 : 7 : 4 : 6. Metatarsomere I thin, straight; 1.8 times longer than length of all rest metatarsomeres combined. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Ventral side sparsely covered with pale semi-adpressed setae. Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Last abdominal ventrite simple, not modified, without incisions or distinct impressions. Pygidium convex, with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 29, 30) thin and long, about 1.7 times as long as wide; with broader basal part and very narrow filament-like apical part (approximately the same length), with more or less smooth transition between them. In lateral view slightly curved. Ventral side of aedeagus slightly convex in basal part and almost flat in apical third. Length of aedeagus about 1.7 mm, width 0.1 mm in basal part and 0.025 mm in apical part.

Females. Four females are similar to male in body colouration, but one female has head, pronotum and scutellum black. All females have not modified elytra with simple lateral margins and without impressions on elytral surface. Spermatheca as in Figs 47, 48. Length of spermatheca 0.25 mm. Body length 4.2–4.7 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n. is easily distinguished from all congeners in the male elytra with triangularly expanded before apex lateral margins and in the presence of cavities on the elytral surface. Before now, only one species of this genus with modified elytra, *S. excavatus* Jacoby, 1884, was known. But it has the elytra with not expanded lateral margins and with impression situated at elytral apex. In addition, this new species differs from congeners in the unusual body colouration: head is black, with the vertex brown, the pronotum is brown (sometimes the head and the pronotum is completely black), the elytra are pale brown. Other *Strobiderus* species have the head completely black or completely brown or brown with the darkened vertex as well as the similarly coloured elytra and the pronotum. In the key proposed by Medvedev and Beneen [2010] *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n. must be placed among species having the elytra with regular rows of punctures and covered with adpressed setae.

Notes. The syntype of *S. excavatus* was examined based on photographs which were kindly provided by Jan Bezděk.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to excavations on its elytra.

Genus *Chaetocnema* Stephens, 1831

Chaetocnema yunnanica Heikertinger, 1951

Material. 2♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1285-1458 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'10", E 99°22'47" 20.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg.”; 6♂, 3♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1285-1525 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'17.4", E 99°23'9.9" 23.V.2025”.

Distribution. China (Yunnan) [Ruan et al., 2019], Thailand (first record).

Genus *Philopona* Weise, 1903

Philopona shima Maulik, 1928

(Fig. 10)

Material. 1♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1285-1525 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'17.4", E 99°23'9.9" 23.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg.”.

Distribution. India (Assam), Myanmar (Momeik, Karen Hills) [Scherer, 1969], Thailand (first record).

Genus *Eudolia* Jacoby, 1885

The species of *Eudolia* were relatively recently reviewed and keyed by Medvedev [2007a]. There are also identification keys to Oriental or Chinese *Eudolia* species in some works [Scherer, 1969; Kimoto, 2000; Medvedev, 2009; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015].

Eudolia doisaketensis sp. n.

(Figs 12, 33, 34, 44, 45, 51)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1099 m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" N 18°57'1.7", E 99°20'34" 17.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg.” Paratypes: 1♂, 1♀ (PR), the same data as in the holotype; 1♂, (PR), the same locality and collector, but “1285-1458 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'10", E 99°22'47" 20.V.2025”; 1♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1105-1186 m N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" N 18°56'49", E 99°21'01" 22.V.2025”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1285-1525 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'17.4", E 99°23'9.9" 23.V.2025”; 1♂, (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 26.V.2025”.

Description. Male, holotype. Labrum pale brown, head and pronotum black, scutellum pitchy brown, elytra metallic blue. Antennae with antennomeres I–III pale brown, antennomere IV partly darkened, antennomeres V–IX black, antennomere X dark brown, antennomere XI brown. Legs pale brown, and metafemora black. Underside of body black. Body length 3.4 mm. General view as in Fig. 12.

Body oblong, convex, slightly broadened posteriorly, 2.12 times as long as wide. Head lustrous. Labrum convex, transverse, with slightly rounded lateral margins and stronger rounded anterior margin; surface with several pale erect setae. Frontoclypeus convex, with slightly triangular-concave anterior margin. Penultimate maxillary palpomere expanded; apical palpomere rather short, triangular. Interantennal space narrow (about 4.5 times narrower than interocular space), convex medially forming rather low keel. Genae short, about 4 times as short as transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles convex, rectangular, with not produced inner anterior angles; close to each other but separated with distinct deep groove; distinctly delimited posteriorly by thin depressed line and somewhat less distinctly delimited anteriorly and laterally. Surface of frontal tubercles glabrous, lustrous. Eyes convex, slightly oval (about 1.2 times as long as wide); interocular space about 1.3 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex convex, lustrous, impunctate, with small depression in front of frontal tubercles. Antennae (Fig. 44) rather robust, about 1.35 times as short as body length. Antennomere I moderately large, widened at apex; antennomere II shortest, with slightly rounded lateral margins. Antennomeres III–IV slightly and antennomere V strongly widened at apex. Antennomere VI enlarged, somewhat barrel-shaped. Antennomeres VII and VIII small, almost cylindrical. Antennomere IX largest, with slightly rounded lateral margins. Antennomere X similar, but smaller than previous one. Last antennomere not long, spear-shaped, but with outer lateral edge slightly triangularly widened in middle. All antennomeres covered with short, adpressed setae; antennomeres III and IV (especially first of them) with additional long protruding setae on

inner edge. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 13 : 5 : 11 : 9 : 10 : 10 : 6 : 6 : 11 : 10 : 10, width ratio as 5 : 4 : 4 : 5 : 6.5 : 7 : 5 : 5 : 7.5 : 6 : 5.

Pronotum narrow and transverse, about 1.37 times as wide as long, broadest at anterior angles, slightly constricted before posterior margin; at level of its posterior angles about 1.5 times narrower than elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin straight for most of length but projecting forward near anterior angles; posterior margin slightly convex. All margins unbordered. Anterior angles bevelled and slightly protruding to sides; posterior angles pointed, distinctly protruding. Lateral margins sinuous, distinctly notched before posterior angles. Anterior and posterior angles with setigerous pore bearing long pale seta. Pronotal surface lustrous and convex, with transverse impression near posterior margin interrupted in middle; almost entirely impunctate except group of punctures in basal depression.

Scutellum about as wide as long, triangular, narrowing towards rounded apex; its surface lustrous without punctures or microsculpture. Elytra 1.57 times as long as wide; slightly widened behind middle with rounded apex. Elytral surface densely punctured with rather large punctures arranged in indistinct rows; interstices lustrous, convex. Humeral calli well developed. Epipleura wide at base, then gradually narrowing and disappearing before apex. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate. Macropterous.

Legs rather long, moderately densely covered with very short adpressed setae. All tibiae slightly widened at apex, without spurs; protibiae slightly curved, meso- and metatibiae almost straight. All tarsomere I not enlarged, narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 7 : 4 : 4 : 9; width ratio of protarsomeres I–III as 4 : 4 : 7. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 9 : 4 : 5 : 10; width ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III as 4 : 4 : 8. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 12 : 5 : 5 : 9; width ratio of metatarsomeres I–III as 4 : 4 : 7. Metatarsomere I elongate, about 1.3 times shorter than next three tarsomeres combined. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Procoxal cavities closed posteriorly. Abdomen with 5 distinctly visible ventrites. Last abdominal ventrite with rounded apical margin. Pygidium convex, with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 33, 34) about 4.5 times as long as wide, widest before acute triangular apex. Ventral side very slightly convex, without depressions. Aedeagus in lateral view slightly curved. Length of aedeagus about 0.7 mm.

Variability. Males are similar to the holotype but one male has pronotum dark brown. Body length 3.3–3.5 mm.

Females are similar to the holotype in body colouration, but have antennae less robust (Fig. 45). Body length 4 mm. Spermatheca as in Fig. 51. Length of spermatheca 0.15 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n. belongs to the species group with the elytra metallic blue and some antennomeres thickened in male and it is more similar to *E. himalayensis* Maulik, 1926 from India (Uttar Pradesh, Sikkim) and *E. birmanica* L. Medvedev, 2007 from Myanmar. The new species is distinguished from the former in the antennomeres V, VI and IX thickened in male (Figs 12, 44), instead of *E. himalayensis* having only V and VI ones thickened. *Eudolia birmanica* (Fig. 11), having almost the same antennae, is the most similar to the new species but differs in stronger and sparser puncturation of elytra (with 11–12 indistinct rows), the body colouration (the head, the pronotum, underside of body and legs are brown) and in the more widened before apex aedeagus with ridge on underside of apical part. *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n. has denser and somewhat finer puncturation of the elytra (with about 15–16 rows), different colouration (the head and the pronotum are black to dark brown, underside of

body and metafemora black), the aedeagus slightly widened before apex and without ridge on underside.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to the collecting locality.

Genus *Hyphasis* Harold, 1877

Hyphasis trilineata L. Medvedev, 2008

Material. 2♂, 2♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Mae Hong Son Pr., Pai Vill., h~560-610 m, N 19°21'41", E 098°27'42" – N 19°22'18", E 098°28'26" 19–21.V.2016 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♀ (PR), “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1105-1121 m N 18°56'51", E 99°21'16" N 18°56'58", E 99°20'54" 10.V.2024 P. Romantsov leg.”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1175-1246 m N 18°56'56", E 99°21'41" – N 18°56'34", E 99°22'15" 19.V.2024”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1285-1458 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'10", E 99°22'47" 20.V.2025”; 2♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1105-1186 m N 18°56'51.2", E 99°21'16.6" – N 18°56'49", E 99°21'01" 22.V.2025”; 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “h~1125 m, at light N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" 29.V.2025”.

Distribution. South Vietnam, Laos [Medvedev, 2009], Thailand (first record).

Genus *Phygasia* Chevrolat, 1836

The species of *Phygasia* were relatively recently reviewed and keyed by Medvedev [2007b]. There are also identification keys to Oriental or Chinese *Phygasia* species in many works [Maulik, 1926; Gressitt, Kimoto, 1963, 2000; Scherer, 1969; Ge et al., 2008, 2010; Medvedev, 2009; Lee, 2012; Chinese leaf beetles, 2015].

Phygasia oblongomaculata sp. n.

(Figs 14, 35, 36, 49)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (ZIN): “N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1437-1350 m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'21.7", E 99°22'36.3" N 18°56'26", E 99°22'02" 24.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg.”. Paratypes: 1♂ (PR), the same data as in the holotype; 1♂, 1♀ (PR), the same locality and collector, but “1125-1400 m N 18°56'45", E 99°21'34" N 18°56'20", E 99°22'19" 16.V.2025”.

Description. Male, holotype. Dorsal side of body black, each elytron with elongate pale brown spot almost touching lateral margin but not reaching suture. Antennae (excluding articulations between three basal antennomeres brown), legs and underside of body black. Body length 5.6 mm. General view as in Fig. 14.

Body oblong, convex, slightly broadened posteriorly, 1.87 times as long as wide. Head lustrous. Labrum convex, transverse, with almost straight lateral margins; its anterior margin entirely covered with several pale setae. Anterior margin of frontoclypeus distinctly raised, triangular-concave. Penultimate maxillary palpomere expanded; apical palpomere short, triangular. Interantennal space rather narrow, about 3.3 times narrower than interocular space, narrowly convex medially forming distinct keel. Genae rather long, about twice shorter than transverse diameter of eye. Frontal tubercles convex, triangular, with produced inner anterior angles; almost touching each other but distinctly separated with groove thin in proximal and wider in distal portions; distinctly delimited posteriorly by thin depressed line. Surface of frontal tubercles uneven, lustrous. Eyes small, slightly convex, oval (1.25 times as long as wide); interocular space about 3 times as wide as transverse diameter of eye. Vertex convex, lustrous, without punctures or depressions. Antennae robust, about 1.4 times as short as body length. Antennomere I moderately large, widened at apex; antennomere II shortest, transverse. Antennomeres III–X slightly flattened and slightly widened at apex. Last antennomere slightly widened distally, then (in apical third) narrows towards sharp apex. Antennomere I rather lustrous

Figs 42–51. Species of the subfamily Galerucinae from Thailand, details of structure.

42 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., male, holotype, elytra; 43 – *Japonitata insolita* sp. n., male, holotype, antenna; 44–45 – *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., antennae: 44 – male, holotype, 45 – female, paratype; 46 – *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n., paratype, spermatheca; 47–48 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., paratypes, spermathecae: 47 – in female with pronotum brown, 48 – in female with pronotum black; 49 – *Phygasia oblongomaculata* sp. n., paratype, spermatheca; 50 – *Sinoluperoides chenchirae*, spermatheca; 51 – *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., paratype, spermatheca.

Рис. 42–51. Виды подсемейства Galerucinae из Таиланда, детали строения.

42 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., самец, голотип, надкрылья; 43 – *Japonitata insolita* sp. n., самец, голотип, усик; 44–45 – *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., усики: 44 – самец, голотип, 45 – самка, паратип; 46 – *Monolepta trizonalis* sp. n., паратип, сперматека; 47–48 – *Strobiderus excavatipennis* sp. n., сперматеки паратипов: 47 – самки с коричневой переднеспинкой, 48 – самки с черной переднеспинкой; 49 – *Phygasia oblongomaculata* sp. n., паратип, сперматека; 50 – *Sinoluperoides chenchirae*, сперматека; 51 – *Eudolia doisaketensis* sp. n., паратип, сперматека.

with rare, short, adpressed setae; rest antennomeres matte, covered with sparse longer semi-adpressed setae as well as denser and shorter, adpressed setae. Length ratio of antennomeres I–XI as 18 : 6 : 14 : 15 : 16.5 : 15 : 15 : 15 : 14 : 13 : 18, width ratio as 9.5 : 7 : 8 : 8 : 8 : 7 : 6.5 : 5 : 5 : 5 : 5.

Pronotum transverse, about 1.8 times as wide as long; at level of its posterior angles 1.25 times as narrow as elytra at level of humeral tubercles. Anterior margin straight for most of length but projecting forward near anterior angles; posterior margin slightly and gently bevelled from posterior angles to almost straight central part; lateral margins distinctly flattened, not quite evenly rounded: widest about in middle, less narrowed anteriorly and more narrowed posteriorly and slightly notched before anterior angles. Anterior and posterior margins bordered only near angles, lateral margins distinctly bordered. Anterior angles blunted and distinctly protruding; posterior angles obtuse, almost not protruding. Pronotal surface convex, lustrous, without distinct punctures, with shallow transverse impression near posterior margin limited on each side with deep longitudinal impression.

Scutellum triangular, about as wide as long, slightly narrowing towards widely rounded apex; its surface lustrous, without punctures but with fine microsculpture. Elytra 1.43 times as long as wide, slightly widened behind middle with rounded apex. Elytral surface densely and confusedly punctured with small distinct punctures; interstices lustrous, flat or very slightly convex. Humeral calli well developed. Epipleura wide at base, then gradually narrowing and disappearing before apex. Epipleural surface lustrous and impunctate. Macropterous.

Legs robust, moderately densely covered with short adpressed setae. All tibiae widened at apex; pro- and mesotibiae without spurs, metatibiae with short apical spurs. Pro- and mesotarsomere I slightly enlarged, with slightly convex upper surface, but narrower than tarsomere III. Length ratio of protarsomeres I–III and V as 11 : 9 : 9 : 15; width ratio of protarsomeres I–III as 9 : 6 : 10. Length ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III and V as 11 : 9 : 8 : 16; width ratio of mesotarsomeres I–III as 8 : 5.5 : 10. Length ratio of metatarsomeres I–III and V as 15 : 9 : 9 : 19; width ratio of metatarsomeres I–III as 7 : 6.5 : 10. Metatarsomere I not enlarged, elongate, 1.73 times shorter than next three tarsomeres combined. Tarsal claws appendiculate.

Procoxal cavities open posteriorly. Abdomen with 5 distinctly visible ventrites. Last abdominal ventrite simple, with rounded apical margin. Pygidium convex, with rounded apex.

Aedeagus (Figs 35, 36) about 3.1 times as long as wide, widest in middle with acute triangular apex. Ventral side very slightly convex without depressions. Aedeagus in lateral view rather strongly curved down at level of anterior third. Length of aedeagus about 1.6 mm.

Variability. Males are similar to the holotype, but have brown spot reaching elytral suture. Body length 4.2–4.9 mm.

Female is similar to the holotype in body colouration, but has antennae less robust. Body length 4.7 mm. Spermatheca as in Fig. 49. Length of spermatheca 0.37 mm.

Differential diagnosis. *Phygasia oblongomaculata* sp. n. belongs to the species group with body (including antennae) black and with a medium size pale spot on each elytron. This group includes also *P. bicoloripes* L. Medvedev, 1995, *P. media* Chen et Wang, 1980, *P. nigricollis* Wang et Yang, 2008, *P. potanini* Lopatin, 1995, *P. pseudomedia* Wang et Yang, 2008 and *P. vietnamica* L. Medvedev, 2007. The new species is distinguished from Chinese members of this group in the aedeagus thin in lateral view (Figs 35, 36) in combination with an absence of longitudinal impressions on the elytra. Among the Chinese species of this group *P. pseudomedia* is most similar to the new species but differs in more robust antennae (Fig. 13) and in the aedeagus thicker in lateral view (Figs 37, 38).

Phygasia oblongomaculata sp. n. differs from *P. vietnamica* (Fig. 15) and *P. potanini* in the aedeagus without longitudinal concavity on ventral side and rather strongly curved apical third in lateral view. In addition, the new species differs from the former in the less elongated body and more rounded lateral margins of the pronotum. *Phygasia bicoloripes* easily differs from this new species and other members of this group in bicoloured legs, not enlarged middle antennomeres of male and the very narrow aedeagus.

Phygasia basalis Kimoto, 2000, *P. indochinensis* L. Medvedev, 1995 and *P. warchalowskii* L. Medvedev, 2007 are also similar to species of this group, but they easy differ from them in the body colouration: antennae are brown, elytra are with brown pattern occupying most of their surface.

Phygasia parva Wang et Yang, 2008 from China having a similar colouration of the elytra is similar to this new species, but can be easily distinguished from it in the pronotum brown and in the shape of aedeagus (Fig. 41).

See also a new identification key for *Phygasia* species with black body and pale spot on each elytron suggested below. This identification key is based primarily on morphological characters and can be used in addition to previously ones based on the colouration of body.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to an oblong pale spot on its elytra.

Auxiliary key to the *Phygasia* species with body black and a pale spot on each elytron

- 1(2). Legs bicolored, aedeagus very narrow, elytra of female with well developed lateral ridge. Antennae more or less filiform, middle antennomeres of male not enlarged. Body length 4.3–5.2 mm. Laos *P. bicoloripes*
- 2(1). Legs black. Antennae of male robust, with middle antennomeres enlarged.
- 3(6). Aedeagus thick in lateral view.
- 4(5). Aedeagus wider, with broadly triangular apex (Fig. 39). Body length 6 mm. China (Yunnan) *P. media*
- 5(4). Aedeagus narrower, with acute-angled apex (Figs 37, 38). Body length 6 mm. China (Guizhou) ...
..... *P. pseudomedia*
- 6(3). Aedeagus thin in lateral view.
- 7(8). Elytra with extended brown pattern occupying most of mid-apical parts (except apex narrowly blacked). Elytral surface with 3–4 shallow longitudinal impressions (more distinct in female). Apex of aedeagus elongated and narrow (Fig. 40). Body length 6.9–8.1 mm. China (Hainan, Guangxi) *P. nigricollis*
- 8(7). Brown pattern on elytra less developed. Elytral surface without longitudinal impressions. Apex of aedeagus not elongated or slightly elongated.
- 9(12). Ventral side of aedeagus with longitudinal concavity. In lateral view, aedeagus more or less evenly curved about in middle.
- 10(11). Body more elongated (Fig. 15). Pale spot on elytra wider (from lateral margin to suture). Body length 6.7 mm. Vietnam *P. vietnamica*

- 11(10). Body less elongated. Pale spot on elytra narrower (far from reaching suture). Body length 4–4.2 mm. China (Sichuan) *P. potanini*
- 12(9). Ventral side of aedeagus (Figs 35, 36) smooth, without longitudinal concavity. In lateral view, aedeagus rather strongly curved about in apical third. Body length 4.2–5.6 mm. Northern Thailand (Chiang Mai) ...
..... *P. oblongomaculata* sp. n.

Genus *Yunotrichia* Chen et Wang, 1980

This very unusual and little-known monotypic genus from the tribe Alticini is characterized by following characters: body long with almost parallel margins, elytra with four longitudinal keels, body covered with adpressed golden hairs, metafemora increased. The specimen I studied from Thailand (Fig. 16) fully complies with all the diagnostic characters of *Y. mediovittata* given in the genus and species descriptions [Chen, Wang, 1980].

Yunotrichia mediovittata Chen, Wang, 1980 (Fig. 16)

Material. 1♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1175-1402 m N 18°56'40", E 99°21'50" N 18°56'39", E 99°22'35" 18.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Distribution. China (Yunnan, Xizang) [Chinese leaf beetles, 2015; Bezděk, Konstantinov, 2024], Thailand (first record).

Genus *Cassida* Linnaeus, 1758 *Cassida rati* Maulik, 1923

Material. 1♀ (PR), "N Thailand, Chiang Mai Pr., Doi Saket Dist., Thep Sadet, h~1285-1525 m N 18°56'24", E 99°21'44" N 18°56'17.4", E 99°23'9.9" 23.V.2025 P. Romantsov leg."

Distribution. China, India, Indonesia, Laos, Myanmar, Vietnam [Yang et al., 2025], Thailand (first record).

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